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Assessing Social Media Usage Patterns Among Undergraduate Students In Sokoto Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the patterns of social media usage among undergraduate students in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria. With the increasing integration of digital technology into daily life, particularly among young adults, understanding how social media platforms are utilized by university students is essential for both academic and social development. The study adopts a descriptive survey design and gathers data from a stratified sample of undergraduate students across multiple tertiary institutions in the metropolis. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data on frequency of use, preferred platforms, purposes of engagement, and the perceived impact of social media on academic performance and social interaction. Results indicate that platforms such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter are the most frequently used, primarily for communication, entertainment, and information access. While many students reported that social media enhances their academic collaboration, a significant number also acknowledged it as a source of distraction. The findings underscore the need for digital literacy initiatives to help students manage their social media engagement more effectively. Recommendations are made for educators and policymakers to integrate social media use constructively within the academic environment.

Keywords: Social Media, Usage Patterns, Undergraduate Students, Sokoto Metropolis

INTRODUCTION

Social media has become an integral part of daily life, especially among university students. Social media refers to the ways of connections among people in which they create, share, and exchange information and ideas in virtual communities and networks (Isah et al, 2022).

In Nigeria, platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram are widely used for communication, information sharing, and entertainment and understanding the patterns of social media usage among

undergraduates is essential for evaluating its impact on academic performance and social interactions (Usman, 2022).

In Sokoto Metropolis, the prevalent use of platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram among undergraduates is obvious and understanding the patterns, purposes, and implications of this usage is crucial for assessing its impact on academic performance, social interactions, and overall well-being (Isah et al, 2022). Aliyu et al (2023) stated that; in Sokoto Metropolis 97.9% of students use social media, with WhatsApp (84.9%) and Facebook (81.7%) being the most frequently used platforms.

The advancement in technologies such as television, computer, social media and internet are predicted to be the agent of deteriorating reading habit among undergraduates students which is a means of entertainment and getting information and enables us to create online means very easily, but part of the side effect is that social media is dropping reading habit and decreasing the level of library patronage by the undergraduate student in the tertiary institutions (Isah et al, 2022).

Oche et al (2019) highlighted various aspects of social media usage among Nigerian undergraduates for instance, a study at Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto found that 97.9% of students used social media, with WhatsApp and Facebook being the most popular platforms. A significant portion (27.4%) spent over three hours daily on these platforms, primarily during nighttime, leading to disrupted sleep patterns and potential academic consequences.

Similar findings were reported in a study at Obafemi Awolowo University, where 97% of students used social media for socialization (83%), accessing information (74%), and academic purposes (73%) and these statistics highlight the multifunctional nature of social media in students' lives, playing roles in both educational and non-educational contexts (Ogunlade & Fasae, 2020).

These findings underscore the need for a comprehensive assessment of social media usage patterns among undergraduates in Sokoto Metropolis. Such an assessment can provide valuable insights into the extent and purposes of social media engagement, as well as its potential effects on academic performance and social interactions. By examining these patterns, this study aims to contribute to the understanding of digital media's role in higher education and inform strategies to optimize its use for academic and personal development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews existing studies on social media usage among undergraduate students, focusing on its prevalence, primary purposes, academic implications, and demographic variations. The aim is to highlight trends, identify research gaps, and establish the foundation for the present study in Sokoto Metropolis.

Prevalence and Popularity of Social Media Among Nigerian Undergraduates

Social media usage among Nigerian university students has become ubiquitous because Fasae and Adegbilero-Iwari (2016) found that 93.5% of education undergraduates in Nigeria use Facebook, followed by Google+ (63.8%) and Twitter (47.8%). Similarly, Singh and Gill (2015) reported that 84.7% of students preferred Facebook, with YouTube (43.6%) and Google+ (41.1%) also being popular choices. These findings underscore the widespread adoption of social media platforms among students.

Purpose of Social Media Usage

The motivations for social media use among students are diverse because Wickramanayake and Jika (2018); Fasae and Adegbilero-Iwari (2016) identified that students primarily use social media for entertainment, communication, and socialization. However, academic-related activities such as accessing educational content and engaging in online discussions were less frequently reported. This trend suggests that while students engage with social media for academic purposes, non-academic activities dominate their usage patterns.

Impact on Academic Performance

The influence of social media on academic performance has been a subject of debate. A study by Ejoh et al (2022) on secondary school students in Onitsha found a negative correlation between social media usage and academic achievement in science subjects and the study attributed this to the time spent on non-academic activities and the potential for distraction. Conversely, a study by Akinwalere and Adeosun

(2022) reported that while social media usage did not significantly affect students' grades, it facilitated communication and access to information, which could indirectly support academic activities.

Gender Differences in Social Media Usage

Gender differences in social media usage patterns have been observed. Fasae and Adegbilero-Iwari (2016) found that female students (63.5%) use social media more than male students (36.5%). This disparity may be influenced by social and cultural factors that affect access to technology and online platforms

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Data were collected from a sample of 400 respondents using a structured questionnaire designed to assess the frequency of social media usage, preferred platforms, purposes of engagement, and participants' perceptions of its impact on academic performance and social interaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the patterns of social media use among students, focusing on the frequency of use, preferred platforms, and primary purposes of engagement. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire in which respondents reported their average daily usage duration and the platforms they accessed most frequently.

Table 1 Summarizes the frequency of social media usage. A substantial proportion of students (67.5%) reported spending three or more hours per day on social media, with 32.5% indicating usage exceeding four hours daily. This indicates a high level of digital engagement among the student population in Sokoto Metropolis.

Table 1: Frequency of Social Media Usage Among Students

Frequency of Use	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Less than 1 hour per day	50	12.5
1–2 hours per day	100	25.0
3–4 hours per day	120	30.0
More than 4 hours per day	130	32.5

Source: Survey Data, 2024

In terms of platform preferences, **Table 2** shows that WhatsApp was the most frequently used social media platform, with 32.5% of respondents reporting its use, followed by Facebook (30%), Instagram (25%), YouTube (6.25%), and Twitter (6.55%). These platforms were primarily utilized for social interaction, entertainment, and academic-related communication.

Table 4.3: Most Frequently Used Social Media Platforms

Social Media Platform	Frequency	Percentage (%)
WhatsApp	130	32.5
Facebook	120	30.0
Instagram	100	25.0
Twitter	25	6.25
YouTube	25	6.25

Source: Survey Data, 2024

These findings highlight the dominant role of mobile-based communication apps in students' daily routines and suggest that social media serves as both a social and academic tool within the student demographic.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the patterns of social media usage among undergraduate students in Sokoto Metropolis, focusing on frequency of use, preferred platforms, purposes of engagement, and perceived impacts on academic performance and social interaction. The findings revealed that a majority of students

engage with social media for three or more hours daily, with WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram emerging as the most frequently used platforms.

Undergraduate students primarily use social media for social interaction, entertainment, and academic-related communication and the platforms offer opportunities for learning and collaboration, extended use particularly beyond four hours daily raises concerns about potential distractions and negative effects on academic focus.

The study contributes to a deeper understanding of how undergraduate students balance their academic and social lives in the digital era. These insights are valuable for educators, policymakers, and institutions aiming to develop strategies that promote responsible and productive social media use among students

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the positive use of social media among undergraduate students in Sokoto metropolis and mitigate its potential negative effects:

1. Promote Digital Literacy Programs: educational institutions should incorporate digital literacy into their curricula to help students develop skills in managing their time online, evaluating online content, and using social media for academic enrichment.
2. Encourage Academic Use of social media: lecturers and academic departments can leverage platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook Groups, and YouTube for distributing educational content, conducting discussions, and fostering collaborative learning among undergraduate students.
3. Implement Time Management Workshops: workshops focused on time management and self-regulation can help undergraduate students become more mindful of the amount of time they spend on social media, particularly for non-academic purposes.
4. Parental and Institutional Support: institutions and parents should work together to monitor and guide students in their use of social media, ensuring a healthy balance between online engagement and academic responsibilities.
5. Further Research: future studies could explore the psychological or cognitive impacts of social media usage patterns, or compare usage across different regions or academic disciplines to gain broader insights.

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